

**Multi-Mode Feedback in Large
Writing Classrooms at Antonine
University (Beirut, Lebanon)
Presented by Nina Kang**

Multi-Mode Feedback in Writing Classrooms

<p>April 22, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Foundations of Assessment in Language Teaching / Principles of Metacognition</p>
<p>April 29, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Whole Class Feedback: Identifying Common Mistakes with a Focus on Grammar & Mechanics</p>
<p>May 6, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Peer Feedback: Targeted Tasks & Discussions</p>
<p>May 13, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Self Feedback: Showcasing Growth through Writing Portfolios & Projects</p>
<p>May 20, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Final Meeting: Review, Presentations of Best Practices</p>

Agenda, Session 5

Review & Discussion of Alternative Grading Systems

Individual Presentations of Best Practices in Multi-Mode Feedback

Break, as needed

Presentations, cont.

Certificate of Completion

Multi-Mode Feedback in Large Writing Classrooms

Workshop Objectives:

- Learn to identify student texts appropriate for modeling feedback on content, stylistic, and grammatical issues
- Introduce and practice using multi-mode feedback strategies
- Develop strategies aimed at helping students to construct their own criteria leading to self-corrections and other self-directed skills

Review: Multi-Mode
Feedback Strategies in
Writing Classrooms

Whole-Class Feedback (WCF): Advantages

- Can alleviate teacher's workload
- Can be used to identify & address learning gaps
- Can help to increase student learning (i.e., studies show improvement in scores and performance-based tasks)

Why Whole-Class Feedback?

Practical

TIMELY

DETAILED

FORMATIVE

Why Whole-
Class
Feedback?

Pedagogically
sound

Explicit Teaching (as opposed
to Identifying Errors)

Responsive Questioning

Live Modelling

Dual Level
Approach:
Whole Class
(in combination
with Individual
Feedback)

WCF – targeted,
instructional,
generalizable

*Individual
Feedback* –
individualized,
catered, specific

Effective Peer Feedback

Guided (teacher led & student sustained)

Structured (with focused tasks or criteria)

Peer
Feedback
vs
Whole-Class
Feedback

Peer Feedback

Focus on Content/Genre

- Audience
- Purpose
- Organization

WCF

Focus on Language

- Grammar
- Mechanics

Best Practices

- Provide clear guidelines and require deliverables (e.g., fill out form)
- Should take place before (not after) the final version of the paper (use for revising, not editing process)
- Repeat use of peer feedback (normalize practice)
- Mix up when and who (e.g., in-class or as homework, in pairs or in small groups)
- Integrate PF tasks into grading system

Self-Feedback

- Offers opportunity to review and reflect upon the development of their writing and communication skills
- Applies meta-cognitive skills (higher-order thinking) to develop strategies and make decisions
- Key to becoming an independent learner (with problem-solving skills)

Self Feedback → Reflective Thinker

- To be effective with self-feedback, students need to develop their ability to think critically
- To help students learn and practice these critical thinking skills, build in time for reflection throughout their work block

Ideas for Self-Feedback

1. Checklist
2. Rubric
3. Portfolio

1. Using a Checklist

- Serves as a useful reminder of expectations and help students to stay focused on tasks
- Ensures all the key elements of a particular type of writing are included
- Can limit student errors (i.e., less instructor comments necessary)

2. Using a Rubric for Self Feedback

A rubric:

- Details the criteria for good work
- Provides important guidelines for students in the writing process
- Can list levels of performance (e.g., numerical scores); or simply list expectations for proficient work
- Can promote “growth mindset”

3. Using a Portfolio for Self-Feedback

Portfolio is a collection of student work which shows student efforts, progress, and achievements

Different types of portfolios include: showcase, growth and evaluation portfolios

Best Practices for Self-Feedback

- Open-ended questions prompt reflective thinking
- Reflection formats provide structure for students' thinking about their work (e.g., reflection sheets, self-evaluation forms, journals)

Part 1: Alternative Approach to Grading

A blue speech bubble with a white border and a small tail pointing downwards, containing the word "Discuss" in white text. The background features several thin, curved lines in shades of gray and blue, some solid and some dashed, creating a sense of motion or flow.

Discuss

- On average, how much time do you spend on grading papers?

Different Types of Grading

- Percentage (Numeric) grading
- Letter grading
- Pass/Fail OR Credit/No Credit
- Norm-referenced grading
- Mastery grading
- Standards grading
- Narrative grading

Limitations of Letter/Number-Based Grading

- Inconsistent measures of student learning and work.
- Implicit biases which can influence how teachers interpret student behavior and effort

Alternative Grading Systems that Foster Student Learning

1. Mastery-Based Education
2. Pass/Fail (Full/Partial/No Credit)
3. Live Feedback
4. Self-Assessments
5. (Digital) Portfolios

Full/Partial/No Credit Assignments

- Not all written assignments need to be “scored/graded”
- Focus on effort and completion
- Use checklists to ensure all requirements are met
- Good for first draft assignments

Live Feedback

- Instructor comments on drafts that require revising/editing
- Whole-Class Feedback as form of live feedback
- Self and Peer Feedbacks as forms of live feedback (grading the “peer” as opposed to the writer; grading based on collaboration and critical reflections)

Self-Assessments

- Method of tracking student progress
- Use of checklists and rubrics to help students measure performance
- Taking Ownership of learning

Portfolios

- Offer a holistic way to assess student progress
- Provides students various opportunities to demonstrate they reached learning objectives and standards
- Does not penalize students for a poor performance on an exam (or for not being a good writer)

Part 2: Individual Presentation of Multi-Mode Feedback

Part 3: Presentation of Certificate

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*thank
you*

